

PACIFICUS

A LITERARY MAGAZINE

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A QUARTERLY PUBLICATION

- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE MEDALS YOU CARRY”

Each medal you wear today... tells a story your story.
A story of sacrifices, *puyat*, and the courage to keep going even when things got tough.

From the medals you first earned in elementary,
to the ribbons in high school,
and now, the recognition you receive in college
every award is proof of your *paningkamot*, *pagtuo*, *ug paglaum*.

Behind every medal you carry are your parents
the quiet heroes who prayed for you every night,
who worked hard so you could study,
and who smiled through the struggles just to see you shine.

Kay para sa mga ginikanan,
bisan kapoy sa trabaho ug daghan problema sa kinabuhi,
pag-abot sa balay, makakita lang sa medals sa ilang mga anak
mawala ilang kakapoy, mawala ang kabalaka,
bisan pa man sa kalisod sa kwarta.
Kay didto nila makita ang tinuod nga bili sa ilang sakripisyo.

These medals are not just made of metal and ribbon.
They are made of *paghago*, *pagtuo*, *ug gugma*.
They carry every sleepless night, every tear,
and every “Kaya nimo na,” whispered when you almost gave up.

So as you wear your medals with pride,
remember: success doesn’t happen overnight.
It grows little by little with faith, hard work, and heart.

You’ve come so far.

And today, these medals you carry are not just symbols of victory
they are the *fruit of your sacrifices,*
the reflection of your strength,
and the *proof that dreams do come true.*

Padayon, anak, sa pagpaningkamot sa pagskwela.
Makab-ot ra gyud ang tanan...
in God's perfect time.

